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KAZAKHSTAN IS A MULTINATIONAL STATE: YESTERDAY AND TODAY

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***Abstract:** The population change in the historical path of the Kazakh people is a great historical event. The deportation of many nationalities to Kazakh lands through a certain policy led to demographic changes. During industrialization, the flow of people coming to Kazakhstan increased, and the majority of the representatives of the nation were Russians. According to the chronological sequence which shows that the number of the Kazakh population decreased and the number of the Russian population increased. The future situation of the population, which had become a minority was described through a social survey on the language issue.*

***Keywords:** USSR, ethnicity/ethnos, Kazakhs, demography, politics, Russian Empire, migration.*

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КАЗАХСТАН — МНОГОНАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ГОСУДАРСТВО: ВЧЕРА, СЕГОДНЯ

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***Аннотация:** Изменение численности населения на историческом пути казахского народа является важным историческим событием. Депортация многих национальностей на казахские земли в рамках определенной политики привела к демографическим изменениям. В период индустриализации увеличился поток людей, приезжающих в Казахстан, и большинство представителей нации составляли русские. Хронологическая последовательность показывает, что численность казахского населения уменьшилась, а численность русского населения увеличилась. Будущее положение меньшинства было описано на основе социологического опроса по языковому вопросу.*

Ключевые слова: СССР, этническая группа, казахи, демография, политика, Российская империя, миграция.

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Introduction. "Where there is unity – there is life," our people say. Thanks to the unity of nations and the friendship of peoples established in our country, our state is thriving and progressing today. The main achievement of our state is the interethnic harmony, mutual understanding and respect among the peoples in our country. The multi-ethnic harmony, solidarity and peace of Kazakhstan are the main wealth of our country. In the historical path of the Kazakh people, becoming a multi-ethnic state and experiencing population changes is a great historical event. The fact that many nationalities came to Kazakh land through a certain policy and were deported led to demographic changes.

Main part. Since the time Kazakhstan became a colony of the Russian Empire, the Kazakhs began to become a minority on their native soil. From the very beginning, when the colonizers organized various expeditions, abolished the khanate, changed the system of government, and began to settle the "surplus" Kazakh lands found during the expedition's research by taking away the local population and settling them with Russian peasants, there were changes in the composition of the local population. According to the 1897 census of the Russian Empire, the number of the Kazakh ethnic group was 3392,8 thousand people [1; p.477].

During the colonial period, as a result of the implementation of the (re)settlement policy of the Russian Empire, the Kazakhs were forced to leave their lands and move around. The first quarter of Soviet power in the history of Kazakhstan is usually considered a period of statehood formation and socio-economic growth. The period from 1917 to 1950 is a very difficult period in the history of the Kazakhs: But these years were marked by stagnation in demographic trends, the consequences of the national liberation movement of 1916 and the "Little October Revolution" after the October Revolution, the famines of 1921-1922, 1932-1933, the years of repression and the consequences of the Great Patriotic War of 1941-1945, the subsequent famine claimed the lives of hundreds of thousands of people. Most of the representatives of the ethnic group were forced to flee from death and emigrate outside their homeland. Direct and indirect deaths of Kazakhs are estimated in millions.

During the period of industrialization, the flow of people coming to Kazakhstan increased. In 1931-1940, the number of workers increased mainly due to the recruitment of labor resources from other enterprises to work at Kazakhstani enterprises. A total of 504 thousand people arrived during this period.

In 1940, another 24241 collective farmers arrived in Kazakhstan from Ukraine and Russia. By 1939, the Kazakhs in the republic had become a minority. So, if in 1926 they made up 57,6% of the population, then in 1939 – they became 38%. The years of industrialization led to an increase in the urban population, urbanization and strengthening of cities. Almost half of the urban population (47,5%) was concentrated in cities with a population of more than 50 thousand people. In 1928-1939 the mechanical increase in the population of Kazakhstan's cities as a result of migration exceeded 1,8 million people. As a result of migration, demographic changes occurred, that is, Kazakhstan became a multinational republic.

During and after the Great Patriotic War, many nationalities were resettled. In fact, this was not resettlement, but rather forced displacement. In the 30s and early 50s of the XXth century, the USSR underwent a series of forced displacements (deportation) of many people, even entire nations. The totalitarian system sealed the fate of millions of citizens. In those years, intellectuals and ordinary working people who defended national interests were innocently persecuted, and later this policy

deprived entire peoples of their homeland in the border region and forcibly deported them to other regions. Kazakhstan was among the main places where they were resettled.

During World War II, Germans living along the Volga River, the North Caucasus, and some peoples living on the Crimean coast were persecuted and forcibly deported to distant lands outside their homelands on the pretext of aiding the Nazi army and regime. Koreans, Chechens, Ingush, Turks, Bulgarians, Crimean Tatars, and representatives of other peoples and ethnic groups who were deported to Kazakhstan on the eve of World War II and during the war years worked in all sectors of the republic's national economy during and after the war, contributing to its prosperity. Despite the decrees of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR and the resolutions of the USSR Government on their return to their homeland in 1957 and the restoration of their national-state structures, the main part of them remained here forever. Only the Caucasian Turks, Germans and Crimean Tatars were not given the opportunity to return to their homelands. Today, they are all equal citizens of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

A lot of information about this is contained in the archive of the Center for Legal Statistics and Information (Deportation) under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Kazakhstan. In 1946, the total number of deportees in the USSR reached 2 463 940 people (other sources say 2 826 419 people). Of these, 1 million 200 thousand people were deported to the Republic of Kazakhstan [2].

According to the report of January 1, 1947, dividing the settlers by nationality: 88650 Chechen-Ingush families (341328 people), 5175 Bulgarian families (18327 people), 10090 Karachay families (37485 people), 101314 German families (325662 persons), 781 Kalmyks (2031 people), 6696 families (27546 people) from Georgia, 1424 families (4039 people) were Crimean Tatars; a total of 255170 families (894687 people) were registered [2].

On January 1, 1948, the total number of forcibly displaced persons into Kazakhstan was 781170 people. They were divided by nationality as follows: Chechen-Ingush - 87860 families (338238 people), Karachay - 10013 families (37019 people), Balkars - 5164 families (18142 people), Germans - 101479 families (343998 people), Kalmyks - 809 families (2137 people), those from Georgia - 6767 families (27210 people), from Crimea - 1549 families (4574 people), and those who were specially deported into the republic in 1949 was registered 250428 families (892671 people). Among them: Chechen-Ingush - 78995 families (299170 people), Germans - 123113 families (410268 people), Greeks - 371108 people, Karachais - 9067 families (33754 people), Balkars - 4772 families (17558 people), Poles - 32652 people, Kalmyks – 765 families (2265 people), immigrants from Georgia - (29699 people), from Crimea 1937 families (5858 people) were registered [2].

Then, in 1949, 36% of the forcibly displaced peoples were resettled on the Kazakh soil, which is twice as many as in all the republics of Central Asia and 6% more than in Western and Eastern Siberia, i.e. 4 out of every 10 people in our republic were representatives of 51 nationalities that were forcibly resettled. Moreover, most of the forcibly displaced peoples were sent to Kazakhstan. In 1949, it was reported that 45400 people were deported to Kyzylorda, Taldykorgan and Almaty regions, and the number of those deported was 57154 people, which is 11714 people more. [3]. For such reasons, the household necessities (shelter, food) that were prepared only for those coming were not enough.

The vast majority of the exiled peoples returned to their homelands. However, due to the circumstances that occurred in their homelands, a certain part of them settled in Central Asia and Kazakhstan. For example, according to the census (1999), the following people settled in the Republic of Kazakhstan: Germans - 353,441 people, Tatars - 248,952 people, Koreans - 99,657 people, Azerbaijanis - 78,295 people, Kurds - 32,764 people, Chechens - 31,799 people, Ingush - 16,893 people [3].

This is the exact data on the peoples deported to Kazakhstan. However, these deported peoples, who were among the equal citizens of the New Kazakhstan – an independent country, continue to make their own contributions to the development of our country in various areas [4].

The situation was complicated by the arrival of hundreds of thousands of evacuees to Kazakhstan during the Great Patriotic War. By the end of 1941, their total number was 386492 people, including more than 136.500 children [4; p.70]. In 1942, 109807 people arrived into the republic from the Voronezh, Stalingrad, Rostov regions and the North Caucasus. They were settled mainly in the north-eastern regions. By the end of 1942, there were 532.500 evacuees in Kazakhstan [4; p.72]. In general, during the war years, the republic received about 1.5 million people evacuated from the occupied regions of the USSR [4; p.66]. The arrival of such a large number of people into the republic compensated for the shortage of labor resources.

The next stage of Moscow's resettlement policy was associated with the development of virgin lands in Kazakhstan. In total, in 1954-1962, about 2 million people came to develop virgin lands. At the same time, more than 300 thousand people from outside the republic came to Kazakhstan's industrial enterprises in 1954-1960, and in 1961-1965, it increased to 500 thousand people, most of whom came from Ukraine, Belarus and Lithuania. In 1965-1975, another 115 thousand people came to Kazakhstan to work at industrial facilities. In 1959-1963, about 200 thousand people returned to Kazakhstan from China. These were citizens who had left their homelands during the war and collectivization periods. Most of them were Kazakhs, Uyghurs and Dungans, although there were also Russians, Tatars, Uzbeks, and Kyrgyz among the returnees [5].

Today, Kazakhstan is Home to more than 130 nationalities and about three thousand religious associations preaching more than 40 religions, based on interethnic and interreligious harmony and compromise. Over the years of independence, Kazakhstan has demonstrated the viability of this strategy and the need for a Kazakhstani model of the culture interaction between peoples in the development of the entire human community. The Kazakhstani model of the culture of mutual interaction between peoples is not only a means of overcoming tension and conflict situations in society, but also of preventing them from escalating into prolonged hostility and eternal hatred in the future. One of the main conditions for preserving the integrity and independence of a multinational state, like Kazakhstan, is the unification of its citizens into a single community, into the rank of a whole people, without dividing them into nationalities and nations that have special advantages and superiority over others [6]. Therefore, the Kazakhstan authorities, while maintaining and preserving the national identity of their citizens, have pursued a policy of unification under the umbrella of the Kazakh nation and around it, as a uniting nation. The Basic Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan states: "No one shall be discriminated against on the basis of their origin, social, official or property status, gender, race, nationality, language, religious affiliation, views and beliefs, place of residence or any other circumstances," allowing its citizens to fully exercise their rights [7].

Conclusion. Obviously, for our common interests and brighter future, for our generation to live in a developed country with interethnic and interreligious harmony, we need to jointly create a "New Kazakhstan" together. As the saying goes, "Kazakhstan is the sacred cradle of peace and friendship", only spiritual harmony between nations and nationalities, between people and people, can form the long-term preservation of any nation. It is not for nothing that our wise ancestors said not for free: "If all four are present, then the one on top will come." We, as a state-forming nation, must promote our national traditions and culture, history and language into the minds of the rising younger generation, while creating opportunities for the preservation of the history, culture and language of other nations, living in Kazakhstan. No one can take over a country where there is harmony, unity and peace. One of the limits of individuality and wisdom is patience. Patience leads to stability. As a country living in one unified family, we must always make the words of respect and dignity our main principles.

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